

ISic1047

I.Sicily inscription 1047

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palazzolo Acreide, Museo Iudica, inventory 2253

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140526

1. [K]ούειντε
2. χ[ρ]ηστὲ καὶ ἄ-
3. μεμπτε
4. χαῖρε.
- 5.

Edition: PHI175463

1. Κουεῖντε
2. χ[ρ]ηστὲ καὶ ἄ-
3. μεμπτε
4. χαῖρε.
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492675
EDCS 39102201
PHI 140526
PHI 175463

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0226 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Pugliese Carratelli, G. 1956. Silloge dell' epigrafi acrensi. In Bernabó Brea, L. (eds.), *Akrai*. Catania. pp. 151-181. At no.30 ph

Ferrua, A 1941. Epigrafica sicula pagana e cristiana. *Rivista di archeologia cristiana*. 18: 151-243. At 198 no.70

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